

Hybrid PZT-FBG Sensing for Damage Detection in Structural Health Monitoring

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Abstract. Piezoelectric transducers (PZT) are very popular in applications related to elastic wave generation and sensing in Structural Health Monitoring. However, the PZT is prone to electromagnetic interferences (EMI). To overcome this problem we propose to perform guided wave sensing using fibre optic FBG strain sensors. In this approach elastic wave generation is based on PZT and sensing on PZT and FBG for the purpose of sensitivity analysis. Based on gathered signals for both types of sensors artificial damage detection is investigated in plate-like structures. Artificial damage in the form of additional mass is utilized.

Keywords: Guided waves, Piezoelectric transducer, Fibre optic sensors.

1 Introduction

All structures are liable to structural damage due to processes of corrosion, wear, or overload. It is very important to assess the state of the structures due to personal safety. For this purpose, structural health monitoring (SHM) systems are designed. There are many SHM techniques, but the elastic guided waves (GW) based technique is very popular nowadays. The most popular transducers in GW-SHM are piezoelectric (PZT). They can be utilized as actuators or sensors. The PZT sensors in the network are connected using electrical wires and are prone to electromagnetic interferences (EMI). To overcome the EMI problem in the case of elastic wave sensing more and more popular are fiber optic strain sensors based on Bragg Grating (FBG). In this case signals are transmitted through the optical waveguides (fibre optic).

FBGs have small diameter, can be embedded in polymer composite structures and can be multiplexed. However, there are passive devices working as sensors. Due to the listed features, they are very promising for SHM sensing purposes. In the case of the use of FBG sensors, elastic wave generation is realized using piezoelectric transducers. Such an approach was utilized for the railways tracks assessment in [1] or rotorcraft structures [2]. It is important to determine the elastic wave sensitivity of FBG sensors [3]. In the case of wave sensing authors of [4] propose passive and active sensing for FBG-based SHM purposes. An interesting approach is a combination of sensing based on PZT and FBG in the form of a hybrid system. This allows to utilize the different sensing properties of both types of sensors. Besides guided wave related research PZT-FBG combination was utilized for voltage sensing [5].

The authors of this paper present results of comparison of the PZT and FBG-based elastic wave sensing from the point of view of the sensitivity and possibility of elastic wave-based damage detection. In this purpose pair of sensors located on the top and bottom surfaces were investigated. This approach was inspired by work [6] where authors utilized pair of PZT transducers. We propose to use the additionally the pair of FBG sensors and to compare both sensing techniques.

Moreover, artificial damage in the form of additional mass is investigated. Differential signals as a result of subtraction referential and damage case signals are utilized for damage index calculation.

2 Measurement setup

The investigated specimen was the aluminum panel with dimensions: $1000 \text{ mm} \times 1000 \text{ mm} \times 1 \text{ mm}$ (Fig. 1). Elastic wave excitation was based on a piezoceramic transducer/actuator (A) in the form of a disc with a diameter of 10 mm and thickness 0.5 mm made out of NCE51 piezoelectric material. The transducer was located in the middle of the panel (Fig. 1). The process of elastic wave sensing was conducted based on a pair of PZT and FBG sensors. For each sensor type they were located on the top and bottom surfaces of the panel. The distance between the sensors and the wave actuation point was 250 mm.

Artificial damage was simulated in the form of additional mass by using a pair of magnets on the top and bottom sides. There were four locations of magnet pairs investigated M1- M4 shown in Fig. 1. In each scenario only one location was investigated.

Fig. 1. Investigated specimen.

The measurement set-up consisted of National Instrument PXIe-5413 waveform generator, piezoelectric signal amplifier Krohn-Hite Model 7500, National Instrument PXIe-5105 oscilloscope card, tunable fiber coupled laser Apex AP1000 (wavelength 1526 nm to 1567 nm), circulator, photodetectors (Menlo Systems, FPD610-FC-NIR), PZT transducers (CTS corporation - former Noliac), and FBG sensors (Femto Fiber-tech).

In the case of PZT sensors, they were connected directly to an oscilloscope card. In the case of elastic wave sensing based on FBG, the edge filtering method was utilized [7],[8]. In this approach tunable laser is tuned to the FBG's reflectivity slope. The middle portion of the reflectivity curve is linear and has a very steep slope. As a result, a little shift in the reflectivity spectrum causes a large change in the optical power sensed by the photodetector. The amplification increases the FBG sensors' sensitivity to elastic waves. The FBG connections are made through a three port circulator. The first port is connected to the laser source, the second to FBG and the third to the amplified photodetector. The photodetector is then connected to the oscilloscope card.

The excitation signal was in the form of five cycles of sine modulated by the Hann window applied to the piezoelectric transducer. The carrier frequency of excitation was in the range of 50 kHz–250 kHz with step 10 kHz.

3 Results

In this section results in the form of comparison of signals gathered by FBG and PZT, and damage index values are presented. Measurements were gathered for referential and artificial damage cases. In the case of the referential state, two sets of measurements were gathered to determine the pristine state of the panel.

3.1 Acquired signals

In Fig. 2 signals for referential R and simulated damage case M1 (Fig. 1) were presented for excitation frequency 50 kHz. In Fig. 2a) a comparison of healthy and damage signals for the FBG sensor located at the bottom surface is presented. Differences in signals are located in the time range ~ 0.3 ms – 0.45 ms. In Fig. 2b) a comparison of healthy and damage signals for the PZT sensor on the bottom surface is presented. Differences in signals are also located in the time range ~ 0.3 ms – 0.45 ms.

The first wave packet (time instance 0.1 ms) is related to S0 wave mode and the second (0.25 ms) to A0 wave mode. For this frequency, the S0 mode has a significantly smaller amplitude than A0.

In Fig. 3 subtracted (differential) signals for referential R and simulated damage case M1 for excitation frequency 50 kHz were presented. In Fig. 3a) results for FBG sensor on the bottom surface are presented while in Fig. 3b) for PZT on the bottom surface. The largest differences in signals for both figures are observed in the time range ~ 0.3 ms – 0.45 ms. These differences are caused by artificial damage M1.

Fig. 2. Signals for referential (R) and simulated damage (M1) case, gathered by: a) FBG, b) PZT; frequency 50 kHz.

Fig. 3. Differential signals, sensing by: a) FBG, b) PZT; frequency 50 kHz.

In Fig. 4 signals for referential R and simulated damage case M3 were presented for excitation frequency 50 kHz. In Fig. 4a) a comparison of healthy and damaged state signals for FBG sensors is presented while in Fig. 4b) for PZT. Both sensors were located on the bottom surface.

Fig. 4. Signals for referential (R) and simulated damage (M3) case, gathered by: a) FBG, b) PZT; frequency 50 kHz.

In Fig. 5 subtracted (differential) signals for referential and simulated damage case M3 (see Fig. 1) for excitation frequency 50 kHz were presented.

Fig. 5. Differential signals, sensing by: a) FBG, b) PZT; frequency 50 kHz.

In Fig. 6 comparison of signals gathered by FBG and PZT sensors located on the bottom surface of the panel for frequencies 50 kHz and 250 kHz is presented. In the case of Fig. 6a) signals gathered for frequency 50 kHz are presented. The first wave packet is related to the S0 wave mode. The second wave packet is related to the A0 wave mode. The amplitude of the A0 mode is approximately ten times larger than that of the S0 wave mode. Signals for PZT and FBG are not in phase, they are shifted but all wave packets correspond to each other.

In the case of Fig. 6b) signals gathered for frequency 250 kHz are presented. The wave packet at time instance ~ 0.5 ms (with the largest amplitude) is related to S0 wave mode. The wave packet at time instance ~ 1.5 ms is related to the A0 wave mode. The amplitude of the S0 mode is larger than that of A0 for this frequency. There are significant differences in signals related to some wave packets. Some wave packets have much larger amplitudes for FBG than for PZT and vice versa. Wave packet at time instant ~ 1.1 ms (located between first S0 and A0 modes arrivals) is gathered by FBG and has a large amplitude while for PZT its amplitude is very small. On the other hand,

wave packet at ~ 0.2 ms sensed by PZT has a large amplitude while a very small amplitude is observed for the case of FBG.

Fig. 6. Comparison of signal for FBG and PZT for frequencies: a) 50 kHz, b) 250 kHz.

In Fig. 7a) a comparison of signals gathered by FBGs on the bottom and top surface of the panel is presented. There are some differences in amplitudes for certain wave packets but all wave packets are present in both signals. In Fig. 7b) a similar comparison of signals gathered by PZT on the bottom surface and top surface of the panel is presented. In the case of PZT placed on the top surface, there is a wave packet at a time instant of ~ 1.1 ms which is not registered by the PZT on the bottom surface. This wave packet was registered by both FBG (Fig. 7a)

Fig. 7. Comparison of signals gathered by pair of sensors: a) FBG, b) PZT; frequency 250 kHz.

In the case of FBG, the differences in wave sensing are caused by the directivity-dependent sensing characteristic of FBG. In Fig. 8 directional sensitivity characteristic for FBG is presented. The FBG was oriented in the direction 0-180°. The sensitivity of the FBG to elastic wave that arrives from a direction perpendicular to the sensor is significantly lower than for parallel direction. The similar observation regarding the directivity of FBG was published in [9].

Fig. 8. Directional sensitivity characteristic for FBG.

However, the lack of wave packet at time instance ~ 1.1 ms in signal gathered by bottom PZT could be caused by the influence of the non-symmetry caused by wrap-around electrodes of utilized PZT sensors. The sensitivity of the PZT could be affected by the orientation of electrodes especially for frequencies above 220 kHz (resonant frequency). The influence of PZT electrodes during the wave generation for frequencies 100 kHz, 150 kHz, and 200 kHz were discussed in [10]. The authors observed that for frequencies 150 kHz and 200 kHz, there were two A0 wave packets generated in one direction. This effect was stronger for the frequency 200 kHz. However, this hypothesis needs to be further investigated by using full wavefield vibrometry-based data.

3.2 Damage detection

In this section signals for frequency range 50 kHz – 250 kHz are utilized for damage detection. For this purpose following damage index (DI) is utilized:

$$DI = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=0}^N (S_R(i) - S_D(i))^2}{N}}$$

where: $S_R(i)$ - signal for referential case, $S_D(i)$ – signal for damage case, N - number of samples. Four damage cases are investigated according to four locations of additional masses M1-M4 according to Fig. 1.

The calculated damage index values for measurement gathered by FBG at the top and bottom surface are presented in Fig. 9a) and Fig. 9b) respectively. In the referential case R, two signals for the pristine state without damage were investigated. Values of DI are larger for damage cases M1-M4 than for referential cases for all frequencies. The largest values of DI are achieved for frequencies about 100 kHz. Similar trends of DI values are achieved for both sensors. Cases M1 and M2 are symmetric but DI values as well as DI trends differ for the sensor on the bottom as well as the top side of the panel.

Fig. 9. Damage index DI for signals gathered by: a) Top FBG, b) Bottom FBG

In Fig. 10 results for signals gathered by PZT located at the top (Fig. 10a) and bottom (Fig. 10b) surface are presented. Results are similar to the case of FBG-based results. The damage cases gave larger DI values than the referential case. The largest values of DI are achieved in the case of a frequency of about 100 kHz. In the case of damage M1 and M2, the results are more similar than for the FBG case.

Fig. 10. Damage index DI for signals gathered by: a) Top PZT, b) Bottom PZT

Obtained damage detection results based on signals gathered by PZT and FBG sensors showed that it was possible to detect artificial damage in four investigated cases.

4 Summary

In this paper authors investigated artificial damage detection for signals gathered by PZT and FBG sensors for the frequency range 50-250 kHz. For damage detection differential signals were utilized. It was shown that damage detection was possible for all investigated wave frequencies as well as investigated artificial damage locations.

Analysis of signals showed some differences in signals gathered by PZT and FBG sensors. Differences in FBG sensing are caused by its directivity. There are also differences between signals gathered by the PZT sensors on the top and bottom surfaces of the panel. These differences could be caused by the non-uniform angular sensitivity characteristics of the PZT sensor caused by the non-symmetric distribution of wrap-around electrodes. This needs to be further investigated.

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